

Project no. **H2020-SMEINST-2-726607**

Project Acronym: **Fastprk-2**

Project title: Enhanced on-street parking management system

Start date of project: 01.06.2016

Duration: 26 months

Project coordinator: Dr. Francisco Hernández-Ramírez

Project coordinator organization: Worldsensing SL

Project website address: <http://fastprk2.eu/>

Deliverable 3.3- Fastprk2 - Product

A. Dissemination Level

PU Public

PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

B. Document details

Work Packages	3
Partners	Worldsensing SL
Authors	Dr. Andrea Bartoli, Dr. Francisco Hernández-Ramírez, Mr. José Gorchs. Inputs from the Engineering Department of Worldsensing SL.
Document ID	3.3
Release Date	17/08/2018

C. Revision history

Version	Date	Changes	Author
1.0	17.08.2018	-	Dr. Francisco Hernández-Ramírez

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0. Executive Summary

Fastprk2 develops a smart on-street parking system to control regulated parking spots with occupancy sensors, aiming to improve the user experience and the parking area management.

This deliverable provides the **overview of the work** done from month 19 to month 26 (M19-M26) of the action to achieve a **final version of the Fastprk2 product**, which is at the time of this writing technologically ready for becoming a commercial product. Most of the technological developments integrated into Fastprk2 were nearly ready in the second release of the prototype at M18. Hence, the work accomplished in this last period of the project has mainly focused on correcting **bugs and errors**, completing some pending tasks such as the final **certification** of the node, designing the **protocols** to deploy the technology in a systematic way and finally, exploring **future technologies** to be adopted by Fastprk2 in the mid-term like NB-IoT.

Since the deliverable is labelled as “*Demonstrator*” in the EC-GA, attached to this document Worldsensing provides direct evidence of the attained results through the programming code of the new software and some flagship demos.

1. Introduction

Fastprk2 has developed a leading end-to-end solution with advanced features compared to the competitors' solutions. To make full use of the potential of Fastprk2, the improved functionalities of the new product range from the certified parking occupancy detection to advanced services offered to end-users, merging the solution with the mobility platform of Worldensing.

The Fastprk2 project relies on a complex system that involves **hardware and software development**, which has been designed to enrich the product portfolio of Worldensing keeping the **equilibrium** between the technological breakthroughs and the commercial priorities.

The project pursued the achievement of **3 different concepts** listed below, which were presented in the deliverables D3.1 and D3.2:

- **Concept 1-** Parking space sensor.
- **Concept 2-** Data management platform.
- **Concept 3-** Transport Services (ITS).

As this is being written, **the final version** of the Fastprk2 product has been **completed** integrating the functional elements in a complete framework, which is already in Worldensing's portfolio.

From month M19, the **technical efforts** have represented the second iteration in the optimization process of Fastprk2, paying special attention to **correct technical bugs**, **certify** the elements of the **sensor node** as well as complete the process to **deploy** the final solution in an **automatic way**. Last but not least, the Transport Services (**ITS**) have been **refined** in close collaboration with ATEKNEA and **new concepts** on NB-IoT have been explored in detailed to, in this way, be ready for updating the communication protocol when necessary.

This deliverable provides the **overview of the work** done in the last months, and it is structured as follows:

- 1) **Update of the progress made at the element level.** This is basically an extension of the activities presented in the deliverable D3.2.
- 2) **Complementary annexes.** A set of documents providing supplementary information is also provided for the sake of clarification of the pending issues identified in this and previous deliverables.

This document is a review of intensive and multifaceted work. For this reason, it is almost impossible to provide full details of each development without tedious and long wording. On the contrary, and since the deliverable is labelled as "*Demonstrator*" in the EC-GA, Worldensing provides attached to this document direct evidence of the attained results through **the programming code of the new software elements and flagship demos**. In comparison with the deliverables D3.1 and D3.2, the document does not go into the technical details, but it deliberately provides a high-level description of the finishing touches done at Fastprk2 technology.

Supporting material	Route
Software code behind Fastprk2	https://www.dropbox.com/s/mbl4j7rd3cy824u/worldensing_traffic-fastprk2-3d73ce924beb.zip?dl=0

The link to the code repository redirects to a DROPBOX folder with the different elements developed in the project.

Nevertheless, the best approach to understand any new system is to interact directly with it. For this reason, demos (software deployed at the pilots) have been put at the disposal of both the EC-GA and the project reviewers at the following links¹:

Pilot	Link
Barcelona (Spain)	https://fp2-barcelona.worldsensing.com/mb/app/
Antwerp (Belgium)	https://fp2-antwerp.worldsensing.com/mb/app/
Wattens (Austria)	https://fp2-wattens.worldsensing.com/mb/app/
Bouffemont (France)	https://fp2-bouffemont.worldsensing.com/mb/app/
Grudziadz (Poland)	https://fp2-grudziadz.worldsensing.com/mb/app/
Los Angeles (US)	https://fp2-losangeles.worldsensing.com/mb/app/

¹ The credentials are sent to the PO via mail for security reasons

2. From the second prototype to the final product

In the deliverables D3.1 and D3.2, the status of development at M14 and M18 of the different elements of Fastprk2 were reviewed in detail. Following the same document structure, the **incremental work** completed since then is presented in this chapter, focusing on the final status of (i) the **parking space sensor (node)**, (ii) the **data management platform** and (iii) the **transport services** (Fig.1).

The main efforts in this third period have **consolidated the interconnection** between the different modules shown below, **improving the stability** of the product as a whole. To that end, the feedback received from the pilots has been extremely helpful. The details of the normal operation of Fastprk2 technology is provided in the deliverable D5.1.

Worldsensing is open to provide any clarification of the work done requested by the EC services

2.1 Fasprk2 node

Fastprk2 nodes (sensors) monitor the presence of vehicles in parking spots, informing the occupation state wirelessly to a central server. They are a core part of the final product developed in the project, and the main details and features have already been presented in the deliverables D3.1 & D3.2.

At M18 of the action the elements at the node level had already been **developed**, and intensive efforts were ongoing to achieve a systematic production process (Fastprk2 fixture). From that time until now, the work related to the node has been as follows:

1. Optimization of the Fasprk2 node firmware

The results from Barcelona and Antwerp pilot revealed serious problems with the detection algorithm of the new tandem IR + magnetic sensor, which could jeopardize the entire project scope if they were not urgently fixed (see the deliverable D5.1). In parallel, some other issues with the normal operation of the node were detected once the sensors worked out of the lab environment (pilot campaign). To solve them, the **node firmware** has partially **remade** from January to May 2018. In fact, 141 individual commits have been necessary to bring the firmware to the final status with almost no errors and leading to the expected detection accuracy values. The chart below shows the distribution of commits per month.

Annex I has a table with a comprehensive list of all the changes done in the firmware code with the corresponding dates, comments and authors. The same code versioning system has been used throughout the duration of the whole project: it is based on *bitbucket* (www.bitbucket.org) and several branches were created to support the releasing of the code without interfering the production tasks. These branches were merged at specific points (24 in total) that can be tracked in the log table. It is interesting to note that the optimization of the IR detection required up to 11 iterations of the code. The detailed analysis of the work done at the firmware level is out of the scope of the document, but further details are available upon request.

2. Optimization of the node box and certifications

As stated in the deliverable D3.2, the first round of certification works revealed that the node box was suitable to be deployed outdoors since it fulfilled the minimum mechanical requirements. Nevertheless, the node encapsulation was just an advanced prototype requiring a complex and manual assembling, raising the overall costs beyond the limits that the market can absorb. For this reason, the **node box** has been **partially rebuilt** so that they can be assembled in an automatic way avoiding the use of screws and resins: it is automatically sealed by means of ultrasounds and offers a vandal proof design (IK10) with a double encapsulation casing material which allows the easy replacement of defective sensors. In parallel, the **certification of the node elements**, mandatory to install Fastprk2 in commercial installations, has required most of the efforts during the last months of the project. Specifically, the following tests have been conducted:

1. **Radio Frequency (RF)** according to the standard 47 CFR (only for LoRa)
2. **Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC)** for LoRa and IR operation:
 - a. EMC tests according to the standards Draft EN 301 489-1 V2.2.0 and Draft EN 301 489-3 V2.1.1.
 - b. EMC tests according to the standard 47 CFR Part 15B, ICES-003 Issue 6.
3. **Electrical Security (ES)** according to the standards EN 60950-1:2006 + A11:2009 + A1:2010 + AC:2011 + A12:2011 + A2:2013.

4. **ROHS Directive 2011/65/UE**: screening of 20 elements. Verification of lead, cadmium, mercury, chromium and bromine.
5. **RF Exposure** Report following the rules IEC 62479:2010, EN 62311:2008, FCC47 CFR part 2.1093, FCC47 CFR part 2.1091 and FCC OET KDB 447498 Do1 General RF Exposure Guidance.
6. Certification procedures and documentation for **US and Canada**.

This work has been mainly completed by external certification companies, but it has required the active involvement of the engineering team of Worldsensing to provide the necessary support and know-how. At the time of this writing, a positive feedback has been received with reference to these tests' results. Nevertheless, the final reports will be available only after summertime.

3. In-depth study of NB-IoT protocol

The **node** of Fastprk2 has been designed to be **compatible with NB-IoT**: the first proof-of-concept devices successfully validated that Fastprk2 can operate with this communication protocol (deliverables D3.1 and D3.2). NB-IoT is destined to become the standard in the coming years, their technical details remain however as the great unknown for SME companies like Worldsensing, particularly regarding the optimized use. This later point is crucial to minimize the power consumption in IoT applications and in particular smart parking solutions operated with batteries.

In this period, Worldsensing has worked in close collaboration of the *Wireless Networks Research Lab of the Open University of Catalonia (UOC)* (<http://wine.rdi.uoc.edu/>) to prepare a detailed internal report on NB-IoT in which different working scenarios have been theoretically defined, evaluated and quantified. As result, a meaningful comparison between LoRa and NB-IoT have been completed, which will serve as the basis for the progressive migration of Fastprk2 deployments to NB-IoT. The final version of the UOC's report is in the *Annex II* of this deliverable.

At M26 the final version of the node is **complete** ready for commercial use. Its performance at single-element level is in-line with the requirements established in the deliverable **D2.1**.

The matching between the initial requirements and the characteristics of the final node is described in *Table 1*. No changes in relation to the second prototype have been added.

Table 1- Fastprk-2 node requirements and matching with the prototype

Req. - ID	Specific description	Comment
RS1	"Detection zone" cone with standard height between 35cm and 60cm	Tests have revealed that the "Detection zone" cone of the prototype covers the range between 35 cm and 100 cm. These values potentially allow the detection of any standard vehicle (from cars to trucks)
RS2	Sensors parameter: "detection zone" cone adjustment	The cone area of the sensor is customizable; the magnetic threshold and the IR power can be easily adjusted with the new calibration tool (RS11)
RS3	Response time less than 10s once a vehicle enters the detection zone	Tandem sensing guarantees a response time of 10s. Operation with only the magnetic sensor increases the time up to 30s

RS4	Normal operation guaranteed for temperatures between -40°C and 85 °C	The new node electronics fulfill the requirement under these conditions
RS5	Normal operation in snowy conditions (15 cm)	The new node fulfills the requirement. Only magnetic detection operational under these conditions
RS6	Normal operation under water conditions (10 mm)	The new node fulfills the requirement. Only magnetic detection operational under these conditions
RS7	Insensitive to dust and dirt	The double technology detection guarantees the resilience against dust and dirt. Outdoors tests have confirmed the good operation performance observed in lab-tests for heavily soiled conditions
RS8	Meet certifications of each component at worldwide level	Components used for the new node development are going through different certification processes such as impact, UV resistance and IP67. The certification of the node elements has been successful
RS9	Detection redundancy system	The sensing procedure of the node based on a new working algorithm and tandem detection have been designed to be energy efficient and redundant. A new firmware version avoids wrong responses coming from contradictory sensors' readouts.
RS10	Insensitive to electromagnetic noise in urban areas	The tandem detection has revealed to be insensitive to electromagnetic noise. In low-noise scenarios (i.e. indoor deployment like airports), a pure magnetic surface sensor remains competitive. In harsh environments, the IR sensor substitutes the magnetic one
RS11	Calibration tool	The node detection baseline is calibrated considering the noise level through an android app running on a smartphone which interacts with the node
RD1	Easy SW updating capability of the sensor	Functionality added through the secondary communication link (RFID) and the calibration tool
RD2	Replicable box	Double-encapsulation box successfully developed

RD5	Robust and low-power communication protocols	Fastprk2 node is Sigfox- and LoRa- ready, with update possibility to NB-IoT. Energy-efficient algorithms developed
RD6	Communication coverage guaranteed	Fastprk2 node is Sigfox and LoRa ready, with update possibility to NB-IoT

2.2 Faspk2 gateway

The gateway is the concentrator that allows the Fastprk2 nodes the data transfer to the Cloud. This device includes some intelligence used to authenticate the nodes with the objective to avoid corrupt data from malicious devices being transferred to the server. This element of the solution's architecture is the less critical for the project implementation since it was already mature in the commercial Fastprk solution before the start of the action. Hence, the **gateway** has been only **partially updated** to fulfil the Fastprk2 requirements, minimizing undesired risks and the internal engineering overhead necessary to build a gateway from scratch.

In the previous period (M1-M18), the technical features of the final Fastprk2 gateway were successfully achieved by modifying a third-party commercial product that had showed excellent results for Worldsensing's technologies in the past. The full details of the work done were provided in the deliverables D3.1 and D3.2: the **stability** of the gateway, **the communication coverage** and the **compatibility** with the new Fastprk2 nodes were checked and validated with excellent results for the project's objectives.

In this last period (M19-M26), the initial **expectations** regarding the gateway have been **validated** during the pilot campaign, distilling practical information about the best strategies to maximize the communication coverage and the optimal working conditions in real deployments. In parallel, the increasing awareness on cybersecurity issues within the company and the participation of Worldsensing in **SMESEC** project (H2020-DS-SC7-2016-740787) has facilitated the preparatory works to develop specific **security tests** to determine that the gateways are not hacked, or their integrity is compromised. Last but not least, Worldsensing has continued **exploring** the integration of **energy harvester** into the gateway. In previous reports, the first proof-of-concept devices were shown, and now their refinement before the market launch will continue in the frame of the R&D regional project **REFER** (ERDF-RIS3CAT-COMRD115-1-0036-05).

The matching between the requirements and the characteristics of the first gateway prototype is described in *Table 2*.

Table 2 - Fastprk-2 gateway requirements and matching with the prototype

Req. - ID	Specific description	Comment
RS4	Normal operation guaranteed for temperatures between -40°C and 85 °C	The new gateway electronics mostly fulfill the requirement under these conditions
RS8	Meet certifications of each component at worldwide level	The LoRa gateway is a commercial product which meets the requirements for standard certifications

RD1	Easy SW updating capability at the sensor / gateway level	The LoRa gateway is remotely accessible and it can be update with the corresponding tool
RD4	Energy cut proof: extra energy availability at gateway level	The LoRa gateway is externally powered and it has an integrated UPS to work for a few minutes after a cut. The integration of PV harvesters to operate the gateway without an external power sources has been completed at prototype level. The system can operate in adverse conditions. Further actions to be conducted beyond the EC-action
RD5	Robust and low-power communications protocols	Fastprk2 can run Sigfox- and LoRa- protocols, with update possibility to NB-IoT. Energy-efficient algorithms developed.
RD7	Communication coverage guaranteed	The minimum levels of the LoRa and Sigfox radio signals are easily achieved in standard deployments. Further exploration of NB-IoT capabilities.
RD8	Maximum number of parking devices managed for each gateway	The maximum number of nodes that can communicate under the coverage of a single gateway is 450 sensors at present time. In the case that more gateways are deployed, the number of devices can increase assuring a high quality of the service.

2.3 Fasprk2 platform

In the previous period (up to M18), Worldsensing actively worked to improve the performance and replicability of Mobility 2.0, moving beyond the first proof-of-concept initially described in the deliverable D3.1: the **internal stability** of the system was improved to run the ITS on top while maintaining the Quality of Service (QoS) of the entire solution at the highest level (deliverable D3.2).

Fastprk2 relies on **Mobility 2.0** which provides tools for **data integration, management** of resources and the advanced **control** of parking facilities and other **assets**. For the sake of simplicity, the BI Aggregation layer is named Mobility 2.0, while the core services of the solution based on the parking commercial solution is identified as Fastprk.

Specifically, actions to correct two specific weaknesses of Mobility 2.0 identified in the previous reports have continued from M19 to M26:

- Standardization of the process of Mobility 2.0 deployment and close monitoring of the operation.
- Evaluation of the GDPR compliance of Fastprk2 related-technologies (sensors and data platform).

2.3.1 Standardization process of Mobility 2.0 deployment

The development of new technical features in a product is crucial for the market success, but also for offering a **robust solution** which can be easily deployed, managed and recovered from unexpected **incidences**. Mobility 2.0 is envisaged as a software platform based on open standards to which third parties can easily integrate. As a result, the software ingests different data sources in a complex approach (huge and heterogeneous amount), which makes necessary a well-defined infrastructure and deployment process to guarantee data interoperability (RP6), data access and resilience (RP5 and RP7), easy scalability (RP9) and failure protection (RP8 and RP10).

To fulfil the abovementioned requirements, the DevOps staff of Worldsensing has continued working in the plan already outlined in the deliverable D3.2, completing the pending work identified in that document:

Improvement 1: Backup

Backup is the process of copying and archiving computer data. It is used to restore the original information after a data loss event. In Fastprk2 platform, there are two main elements to backup:

- Files (static & dynamic).
- Databases.

Procedures to save both types of data have been **implemented** by DevOps together with a simple recovery process. Besides, another important piece in the development of Fasprk2 has been structuring stable **software repositories** which are easily accessible at any time. Further details are available upon request.

Improvement 2: Upgrade

Upgrading is the process of replacing a product with a newer version of the product software. Fastprk2 consists of a complex platform architecture composed of various software products that are likely to change over time due to security fixes, technical improvements, and new features added by third parties. Therefore, the final objective is to upgrade Fastprk2 without affecting the software stability and the final functionality.

Development environment

Special attention has been given to document and establish procedures so that third-parties can develop their own connectors and provide new data to our platform in a systematic and homogeneous approach through a well-controlled development environment. The final objective is to have a modular solution which can be adapted to the customer requests in a simple way. Further details are available upon request.

Improvement 3: Towards a distributed system

Given the microservice-based architecture of Mobility 2.0, a large number of containers, which can be even installed in different physical systems, needs to be simultaneously managed. In this sense, a solution to do this scalable and with a production-ready approach had to be implemented.

Finally, *Portainer* (<https://portainer.io/>) was adopted as an alternative to Kubernetes: *Portainer* is a lightweight management UI which allows a straightforward deployment and an easy management of Docker environments (Docker hosts or Swarm clusters). It consists of a single container that can run on any Docker engine (Linux or Windows) and it is specifically designed to monitor and control critical processes. In Faspitrk2, *Portainer* has been deployed in each pilot. The credentials to these software instances are available upon request.

Improvement 4: Infrastructure Monitoring Automatization

To guarantee the platform functionalities, automatized monitoring tools needed to be developed. Moving from the initial conception outlined at M18, the DevOps department has completed a self-intuitive GUI that generates real-time charts of KPIs that can be freely defined by the users. In this way, different metrics can be controlled by the platform administrators. This solution has been successfully tested in the frame of the pilots' campaign. Following, some examples of the tool are shown:

Total processes

Memory GigaBytes used

Main screen of the system (Fastprk2 filtered)

Pilot in Antwerp (real-time monitoring with monthly figures)

Pilot in Antwerp (real-time monitoring with daily figures)

Data inspection of one of the charts (CPU consumption for each one of the Docker containers)

2.3.2 Evaluation of the compliance with GDPR

The entry into force of the GDPR (EU 2016/679) is at the same time a huge challenge but an opportunity for WorldSensing. The use of heterogeneous data in the frame of Fastprk2 requires an accurate analysis of the underlying technology according to the Art.35 of the Rule. Following the work done in collaboration with specialized advisors (Herrero y Asociados SL, www.herreroyasociados.com), who assist WorldSensing in the process of adaptation of the internal procedures to the GDPR provisions, Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) reports have been prepared for both Fastprk2 as a mere parking technology and Mobility 2.0 (data platform). As expected, the use of **Fastprk2** is fully **compliant** with the **GDPR provisions** while further work is needed to demonstrate the compliance of the platform with art.5 of the Rule: since Mobility 2.0 can ingest different data sources, the eventual processing of those classified under the art.9 of the GDPR (special categories of personal data) could lead to a high-risk scenario if they are not correctly handled. Despite this has not occurred so far, WorldSensing is actively working to adopt the best privacy by design strategies and respect the accountability principle foreseen in the new legislation. For the sake of transparency, the two DPIA (Spanish version) reports are shown in *Annex III* of this deliverable.

Table 3- Fastprk-2 platform requirements and matching with the prototype

Req. -ID	Specific description	Comment
RP1	Only accept approved sensor messages	Messages sent by the nodes are encrypted. Those with incidences are discarded when received
RP2	Ability to ingest parking and traffic messages at an enormous rate (linear scaling)	Data ingestion is based on queues to guarantee that messages are not lost, and the system is slowed down
RP3	Message resilience – once accepted it is not lost and it can be replayed if needed	Data ingestion is based on queues to guarantee that messages are not lost. Raw data are stored in a shared database.
RP4	Low latency of message and data processing to allow live updates of data	The architecture of Fastprk2 is designed to horizontally scale. In this way, the applications with real-time data requirements can quickly access them, no matter how large the number of nodes is
RP5	Data access for services can scale linearly for large request volumes	The architecture of Fastprk2 is designed to horizontally scale and serve many requests. Mobility 2.0 is based on the use of Microservices and it can be easily replicated.
RP6	Data interoperability via integrations with other platforms should be straightforward for both consuming and exporting data	Mobility 2.0 is deliberately designed to integrate data from several sources. Fastprk2 also offers tools to interact with other systems without going through the Mobility 2.0
RP7	Data storage is resilient to failures	Fastprk2 uses a replicated database to allow transparent failure tolerance. Mobility 2.0 databases are treated as pets with careful configuration and maintenance efforts. Resilience is obtained by a combination of infrastructure (RAID disks separated from the physical machines, virtualization) and system-specific tools like master-slave replication. A high-level disaster recovery plan has been drafted, and it will be adapted to the specific deployment in a case-by-case approach.

RP8	Services are resilient to failures with automatic failover	Critical components of Fastprk2 are replicated. Mobility 2.0 is structured on microservices, which are also replicated to guarantee the availability and minimize failures effects. The final architecture will be managed by Portainer.
RP9	Elastic provisioning provides automated machine resource increases and automated deployments to maintain a service-level policy	Mobility 2.0 will automatically control the number of replicas of each microservice by using the machines assigned to the Portainer cluster. The number of machines in the cluster can also be dynamically managed. Fastprk2 system is designed to horizontally scale.
RP10	Disaster recovery – the entire platform must be able to be hot deployed in a new facility or switched to a failover within 1 hour	Mobility 2.0 is easy to deploy and manage, since most of the steps are automated using <i>Docker</i> , <i>Docker Compose</i> and Portainer. Similarly, Fastprk2 is also deployable inside containers and easy to install. Then, the full Fastprk2 platform can be easily recovered from a recent data backup.

2.4 Faspark2 Services

In this section, the latest enhancement and updates introduced into the ITS from M19 to M26 are briefly reviewed: this period has been above all characterised by the deployment of the **ITS suite at the pilots** and the evaluation of its benefits. In the usual way, several bugs found during the campaign have been fixed such as the wrong graphical presentation of the parking forecasting data.

As shown in the deliverable D5.1, the ITS have worked as a rule well and minor changes have been needed compared to the SoA presented in the deliverable D3.2. In fact, the technical efforts have mainly focused on ensuring the proper functioning of the different demos for six months, with the exception of the enforcement service.

As explained elsewhere, this service has caught the attention of different stakeholders such as the Barcelona Municipal Services (BSM, www.bsmsa.cat/en/), and consequently, Worldsensing decided to improve the first version, designed only for demo purposes, to a more mature technology status (TRL9) suitable for commercial actions. Among the improvements resulting from this work, the following actions should be particularly underlined:

1. Service **backend** that consumes data and applies complex business logic rules to publish alerts about the potential violations;
2. **Frontend** that collects the backend outputs, rendering them with the company's look and feel.

In fact, the enforcement service is ready to alert if individual violations occur for those vehicles being tracked, and it provides meaningful statistics about the events occurring in each area.

Frontend: “Event management view”. The service returns individual alarm messages for those vehicles being tracked. This functionality is used by public authorities in some situations

Frontend: “Graphical view”. The service provides useful statistics of the legal offences in an area so that authorities and city operators can develop corrective actions (i.e. optimized routes of parking controllers).

All in all, the services foreseen in the EC-GA have achieved a maturity level high enough to validate their functionality. Nevertheless, the enforcement example has revealed that they all will require additional efforts of adaptation once they are finally on the market.

The matching between the requirements and the characteristics of the services are described in Table 5.

Table 4- Fastprk-2 service requirements and matching with the prototype

Req. -ID	Specific description	Comment
RP5	Data access for services can scale linearly for large request volumes	The architecture of Fastprk2 is designed to horizontally scale and serve many requests. Mobility 2.0 is based on the use of Microservices and it can be easily replicated.
RP6	Data interoperability via integrations with other platforms should be straightforward for both consuming and exporting data	Mobility 2.0 is deliberately designed to integrate data from several sources. Fastprk2 also offers own tools to interact with other systems without going through the Mobility 2.0. Services provided by Third Parties will be available in the final version of Fastprk2
RP7	Data storage is resilient to failures	Fastprk2 uses a replicated database to allow transparent failure tolerance. Mobility 2.0 databases are treated as pets with careful configuration and maintenance efforts. Resilience is obtained by a combination of infrastructure (RAID disks separated from the physical machines, virtualization) and system-specific tools like master-slave replication. A high-level disaster recovery plan has been drafted, and it will be adapted to the specific deployment in a case-by-case approach.
RP8	Services are resilient to failures with automatic failover	Critical components of Fastprk2 are replicated. Mobility 2.0 is structured on microservices, which are also replicated to guarantee the availability and minimize failures effects. The final architecture will be managed by Portainer.
RP9	Elastic provisioning provides automated machine resource increases and automated deployments to maintain a service-level policy	Mobility 2.0 will automatically control the number of replicas of each microservice by using the machines assigned to the Portainer cluster. The number of machines in the cluster can also be dynamically managed. Fastprk2 system is designed to horizontally scale.
RA1	Data insights	Mobility 2.0 is easy to deploy and manage, since most of the steps are automated using <i>Docker</i> , <i>Docker Compose</i> and Portainer. Similarly, Fastprk2 is also deployable inside containers and easy to install. Then, the full Fastprk2 platform can be easily recovered from a recent data backup.
RA2	Modelling of the data	The models describing traffic and parking systems have been completed to theoretically support Fastprk2 services. Near future variables of the systems can be already estimated as well as infer spatiotemporal
RA3	Analysis of the Spatiotemporal correlations	

	of the data	correlations. Machine Learning techniques are a core part of Mobility 2.0.
RA4	Analysis of more suitable Machine Learning techniques	
RA5	Data filtering and metadata segmentation	Segmentation and filtering of data is done at the “feature extraction” module of Fastprk2
RA6	Data visualization tools	Visualization tools from the commercial Mobility platform of Worldsensing have been adapted and updated in Mobility 2.0. The final services supporting Fastprk2 product have been developed during the pilots’ stage

2.5 Conclusions

This deliverable summarizes the work done during the last stage of development of the project leading to the release of Fastprk2 product (T3.5). Following the EC-GA schedule, the second version of the prototype has been optimized through the validation activities of WP5 (pilot campaign), and the operational processes to offer a cost-effective solution have been developed and put in place. Details about the ISO certification at the company level and the business impacts of Fastprk2 are provided in other deliverables.

Abbreviations

Acronym

BI
D
DPIA
EC-GA
EMC
ES
EU
GDPR
IR
ITS
LoRaWAN
M
NB-IoT
PV
QoS
RF
RFID
ROHS
SME
SoA
SW
TRL
US
WS

Full name

Business Intelligence
Deliverable
Data Protection Impact Assessment
Grant Agreement
Electromagnetic Compatibility
Electrical Security
European Union
General Data Protection Regulation
Infrared
Intelligent Transport Services
Low Power Wide Area Network
Month
Narrow-Band IoT
Photovoltaics
Quality of Service
Radio Frequency
Radio Frequency Identification
Restriction of Hazardous Substances Directive
Small and Medium Enterprise
State-of-the-Art
Software
Technology Readiness Level
United States
Worldsensing

Annexes

On the following pages, a set of annexes is presented to supplement the information given in the deliverable as well to provide the necessary context to evaluate the work done so far. The annexes are the following ones:

Annex	Title	Comment
I	List of commitments to update the node firmware	Text extracted from internal working documents
II	NB-IoT report	Report on NB-IoT and comparison with LoRa
III	DPIA of Fastprk2	Reports of Fastprk2 and Mobility2.0

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